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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 3

Pages: 339-351

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3063

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14885203

Manuscript Accepted: 10-04-2024

Motivational Strategies as Predictor of Teacher's Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine which domain in the school heads' motivational strategies predicted the job satisfaction of teachers significantly. The study utilized the quantitative non-experimental research design using causal-effect technique. The respondents were 165 public elementary teachers of Talaingod Municipality. Random sampling technique was used in the selection of the respondents of this study. The statistical tools used for the interpretation of the results in the study were Mean, Pearson-r and Regression Analysis. This study revealed a high level of motivational strategies in terms of staff development, staff recognition and professional advancement. This also displayed a high level of job satisfaction among teachers in work itself, advancement opportunities, supervisor support and co-worker relations. The correlation coefficient between the study's two variables revealed a high positive significant relationship. Staff development, staff recognition and professional advancement were revealed as the domains of motivational strategies that best predicted the job satisfaction of teachers.

Keywords: *MAED-Educational Management, motivational strategies, job satisfaction, Philippines*

Introduction

In the field of education, work satisfaction of teachers is one of the focal points of numerous researches. Teachers with a high job satisfaction are more committed to the work and have less chance of leaving the field to pursue another occupation (Brantley-Dias, Larkin & Lokey-Vaga, 2016). In North Carolina, teachers' job satisfaction is a rampant problem that their educational system is struggling. Surveys in the said place studied factors contributing to teachers' job dissatisfaction that leads to parting or finding a new work (Horowitz, Markow & Moessner, 2006). Moreover, it has been acknowledged that the effects of low job satisfaction are truancy, indiscretion and the lack of commitment (Akyeampong & Bennell, 2007). In fact, teachers' low level of job satisfaction brings down the number of teaching force in the field (Arnold & Otto, 2005). Also, worker satisfaction has a significant influence on their working efficiency (Furnham, 2005).

In the Philippine setting, a particular study emphasized that work satisfaction significantly affected teacher efficiency (Antok et al., 2017). In addition, job satisfaction is a vital component which measures the feelings of workforces about their labor (Bono, Judge, Patton & Thoresen, 2001; Ostroff, 1992). Valuing work satisfaction of teachers affects productivity levels (Arnold & Otto, 2005) and quality of instruction (Demirtas, 2010). Also, teachers are the key players in achieving the aims and priorities of the organization and they are key people who shape the students to excellence in their careers. Additionally, the satisfaction of teacher jobs could be defined as a positive emotional state that results in self-esteem. Also, teachers with high job satisfaction are able to give higher quality teaching to the students and bring greater opportunity to succeed (Demirtas, 2010). Besides, the level of job satisfaction in the Philippines fell from 5.25 in 2016 to its current 10-point ranking of 4.97 in a survey. It has been discovered that the main factors contributing to job discontent are lack of career growth, training programs and administrator management (JobStreet, 2017).

Motivation in the local environment has a major impact on teachers' satisfaction to work, especially as most schools are located in far-flung areas. The circumstances encountered by the teachers need ample determination to be satisfied and perform well. The connection between the management style of school heads, including motivational techniques and the willingness of teachers to do their jobs, is accentuated by several researches (Dou et al., 2016; Ling & Ling, 2012; Raman et al., 2015). It has been illustrated, along with diverse notions of motivation and job satisfaction, that both have a relation (Aziri, 2011). Employee satisfaction is linked with positive behavior driven by motivation, as reported by Dawson (2005). The reward system available to the teaching profession goes a long way to determine how the teachers are doing their work. Incentive scheme in every organization is a way to keep those employees at work.

Given the circumstances, the researcher came across to directly pursue the study. In fact, the result from various literature reviews showed that turnover among teachers was still in high level. It was also added that public school teachers have bigger chance of shifting work while others moved from another institution that offered high salary rate. Most researchers found that teachers who were extremely pleased with their work were expected to execute high-quality performance and were less likely to leave or change their work (Brantley Dias, Lokey-Vega & Larkin, 2016). This situation denotes a need to determine about the effect of motivational strategies to work satisfaction of teachers. There are many researches that scrutinized which of which really affect teacher job satisfaction but still the degree to which motivational strategies especially non-monetary incentives influence teacher performance is not yet understood in society and satisfaction at work. Hence, this study augmented another stratum towards understanding what triggered a teacher to be satisfied and stay in the field.

Research Questions

The main aim of this study was to find out which domain in motivational strategies of school heads that significantly predicted teacher's

job satisfaction. Specifically, it aimed to provide responses to the following:

1. To determine the influence of motivational strategies by school heads on teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. staff development;
 - 1.2. staff recognition; and
 - 1.3. professional advancement
2. To determine the level of job satisfaction of teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. work itself;
 - 2.2. advancement opportunities;
 - 2.3. supervisor support; and
 - 2.4. co-worker relations
3. To determine the significant relationship between motivational strategies and job satisfaction.
4. To determine which domain in motivational strategies of school heads that significantly predicts teacher's job satisfaction.

Methodology

Research Design

This study embraced the survey research scheme employing causal-effect technique. Survey study is one of the popular methods used in quantitative research where the data will be obtained using questionnaires. Also, causal-effect method reveals the relationship of two variables and how one influences the other (Creswell, 2012). Further, this study is indeed apt to the above stated designs since profound analysis is needed in the phenomena (Cooper, 1996). In fact, the said research design will allow the study to determine the influence of motivational strategies to the job satisfaction of teachers.

More so, survey studies are types of quantitative study in which the researcher administers a survey to a sample or to an entire group of individuals to classify the attitudes, values, habits or characteristics of the population. The researcher is using questionnaire to gather the data through this method. Besides, this research uses the concept to demonstrate how motivational techniques employed by the heads of schools influence teachers' job satisfaction (Creswell 2005). Furthermore, the aforementioned design is suitable because it involves an intense and comprehensive collection of data from a given group (sample) in a certain field involving data collection questionnaire techniques. Hence, the findings will nevertheless provide important information that will augment for more researches about the said area that is why there is a need to adopt such research design.

Respondents

In this study, the targeted population includes public elementary teachers of Talaingod District. This particular group was randomly selected by the researcher. However, the respondents can withdraw anytime if they think it was not favorable and felt threaten. The total number of teachers was 280. To achieve the best sample size for population, the researcher used Slovin's formula to engage in random sampling technique.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Population</i>
A	9
B	12
C	7
D	10
E	8
F	10
G	8
H	7
I	9
J	10
K	23
L	17
M	4
N	19
O	12
Total	165

In this study, the researcher expressed the inclusion and exclusion criteria. For inclusion criteria, the respondents were male and female elementary teachers assigned in accessible public elementary schools located in Talaingod District. On the other hand, exclusion criteria consisted of secondary teachers teaching in Talaingod District, public schools located in Talaingod District which is inaccessible and schools located outside Talaingod District. The respondents can withdraw anytime if they felt threatened in the conduct of the study. More so, the respondents were given the right to decide not to answer questions which made them felt any psychological or emotional distress and cannot discuss the information being asked without penalty and without providing reason. Hence, the criteria determined

the scope and validity of systematic review results.

Instrument

In this study, the researcher used downloaded, adopted and modified two sets of questionnaires. This was administered to the selected teachers to determine how school head's motivational strategies affected their job satisfaction. Moreover, each tool was partitioned into two portions. First part was demographic profile of respondents, while second part included a set of questions intended to collect information on the variables from the respondents. The used questionnaires were content-validated by the experts to assure validity. It had been emphasized that accuracy of interpretations based on the results is one of the essential features of a research (Shaun, 2002). A preliminary examination to determine the authenticity of the questionnaires was executed. The individuals who participated in the initial test were removed from the final test. To guarantee the study's authenticity and consistency, it was definitely conducted.

Moreover, the first set of survey form was constructed to take feedback from the educators on the influence of school head's motivational strategies on job satisfaction with the following indicators: (1) staff development; (2) staff recognition and (3) professional advancement. For each indicator there will be corresponding scale to what range the respondent agree or disagree to the given statements: 5 (always); 4 (often); 3(sometimes); 2(seldom) and 1(never).

Additionally, for the second set of questionnaire, it was intended to collect data on satisfaction of the teachers towards their work with the following indicators: (1) promotion opportunities, (2) working condition and (3) job security. The questionnaire will be rated by the respondents with these scales: 5 (Most satisfied); 4 (satisfied); 3(undetermined); 2(slightly satisfied); and 1(unsatisfied).

Procedure

Data for this study were gathered through the following steps. First, after the thesis committee approved the proposed study, the researcher created the data gathering instrument. The constructed questionnaire was hand over to the adviser for further suggestions and modifications. After checking the crafted questionnaire, it was finalized and forwarded to the experts for validation. Then, the researcher sought consent to conduct the study among public elementary teachers in Talaingod District.

Subsequently, after making the permission letter, it was signed and granted by the Department of Education-Davao del Norte spearheaded by Davao del Norte Division Superintendent. Upon the approval of the Superintendent, a copy of approved letter was handed to Talaingod District Supervisor. It was carried out to the school heads and then the researcher personally administered the survey tool but before distributing the questionnaires to the respondents, the researcher gave first the directions to obtain precise result. Moreover, the distribution of the questionnaire to the respondents was within October to December 2019. The questionnaire requires approximately 5 to 10 minutes to finish. Afterwards, the researcher collected the distributed questionnaire. Lastly, collected data was tallied for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Data gathered were analyzed using the following statistical tools:

Mean. This was used to give on point description of the level of exposure on motivational strategies and job satisfaction.

Pearson-r. This was utilized to determine the relationship between job satisfaction and motivational strategies.

Regression Analysis. This was applied to determine what domain in the motivational strategies of school head influences the job satisfaction of teacher.

Ethical Considerations

This research was guided by ethical considerations throughout its phases. There are essential principles that almost studies give emphasis, these are the right to conduct the study, confidentiality and anonymity. Also, the researcher identified and followed full moral standards in the run of the study upholding the study code of ethics and the guidelines provided, in particular by extracting key ideas from various sources including such, but it's not restricted to:

Voluntary participation. The public elementary teachers from Talaingod District, Davao del Norte as respondents of the study were granted the opportunity to participate with no impact or expense, including reduced benefits. Hence the rights of the respondents to add to this collection of information after serving the intention and delivering, explaining and presenting the benefits to the entities concerned.

Privacy and confidentiality. To address privacy and confidentiality during data gathering, the researcher first presented agreements and discussed to the respondents how their data will be used in the study. Also, to protect privacy, respondents are not required to put their name, address, station and other information to the questionnaire that can give away hint. After the conduct of study, the researcher kept the personal information of the respondents in private and with utmost confidentiality as provided in protocols.

Informed consent process. The survey questionnaires are fully available in technical terms, which made it much easier for the research participants. It provides the survey participants a clearer picture of the beneficial effects they'll gain after carrying out this research. Moreover, studied respondents are completely briefed about the procedures, advantages and possibilities before answering.

Recruitment. To get a saturated form of data, respondents were randomly selected by the researcher. Terms and definitions were being identified to determine the best and provided the needed data. Furthermore, the researcher must obtain permission to perform the research before collecting the data. The letter of request was authorized and confirmed by the Department of Education-Davao del Norte spearheaded by Davao del Norte Division Superintendent. Upon the approval, a copy of approved letter was handed to Talaingod District Supervisor and carried out to the school heads. Then, the researcher personally administered the survey tool.

Risks. The study did not involve any risky situations that the respondents of the study may have experienced in physical, psychological or socio-economic concerns. The study only engaged in the knowledge, expertise and experiences of the respondents.

Benefits. Different groups of people will benefit on the study. The findings are useful to the society since it brings information that enable people to understand the importance of motivation and how it can affect a person in terms on job satisfaction. Moreover, the research will help education providers understand the scope of their efforts to inspire and attract competent educators. Also, to the school principal: for them to distinguish strategies to amend the performance of teachers, find ways to help improve teacher morale and alleviate the factors that decrease teachers' satisfaction; teachers: for them to know the impact of motivation to their job and adjust to situations; and researchers: make use of the study results as a basis to develop the performance of teachers in school. Lastly, the study welfares Department of Education administrators of Davao del Norte Division and Talaingod District in terms of motivational strategies and to validate the influence of strategies towards job satisfaction.

Plagiarism. Ensured that there is no evidence of copying any part of anyone's research and the study has no misrepresentation of other's work. In fact, the study underwent plagiarism detector or any similarity index test such as Grammarly and Turnitin software.

Fabrication. The research output was free of intentional misinterpretation of what has been already crafted. The study did not compile data and results, or deliberately drew inappropriate conclusions. In order to avoid such kind of circumstance in the research, the researcher directly administered the survey forms to ensure a full collection of data. Also, the researcher made sure that the gathered literature reviews were all in line and support the claim of the study. More so, conducting intensive review of the collected data was also a way of giving precise result on the study. Thus, the said procedures helped avert this kind of misconduct.

Falsification. Ensured that there was no such act or part of the study which were purposefully misrepresenting the work just to fit the study. Excessive claiming and exaggeration of facts and data were carefully avoided. In order to avoid this kind of situation, the researcher underwent validation (internal and external validation) of the questionnaire to check its authenticity and consistency. Also, the outline of the research has been evaluated before proceeding with data collection through a review (ethics review). Hence, through the aforementioned procedures misrepresentation of the study will be averted.

Conflict of Interest (COI). To stress, conflict of interest was strictly avoided. Personal judgment and views were set aside. Bases of the results, conclusions and recommendations were purely base from the gathered data which underwent analysis and interpretation. Moreover, the study was not sponsored by any government or non-government organization. Further, all processes adopted were in accordance with the committee's ethical principles. Hence, the results were purely objective and based on the information collected. Body of experts and specialists must evaluate the data to arrive at appropriate and reliable conclusions.

Deceit. There's no evidence from the research that the informants were fooled into any possible damage. To avoid this kind of misconduct, the investigator provided the respondents with short, straightforward and concise explanations as to the intent of the research to provide adequate context in the research. Also, the researcher revealed other important subjects such as methods about the study at the earliest possible time for the respondents to decide uprightly. Thus, the procedures helped the respondents not to be at risk.

Permission from Organization/Location. Prior to the commencement of data collection, the researcher sought consent to conduct the study among public elementary teachers in the Talaingod District. Consequently, after making the permission letter, it was signed and granted by the Department of Education-Davao del Norte spearheaded by Davao del Norte Division Superintendent. Upon the approval of the Superintendent, a copy of approved letter was handed to Talaingod District Supervisor and carried out to the school head of the selected public elementary schools.

Authorship. The researcher was a public elementary teacher of Talaingod District, Davao del Norte Division. More so, the study underwent multiple processes to produce a valid and standard research. Besides, the paper was passed through series of revisions due to adviser's suggestions and inputs that enable the researcher to critically analyze the obtained data and incorporate it with existing related studies to support the claim. Further, the study must follow policies and guidelines that are similar to the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee requirements. The researcher sent manuscript and other pertinent attachments to the review committee as foundation implementing ethical considerations. After the approval, the data collection started and interpreted in the later part.

Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter are the analysis, interpretation and results of the collected data from the data collection instrument used in the study to find out what domain would significantly predicts the motivational strategies to job satisfaction of teachers.

It has been noted that the standard deviation is ranged from 0.463 to 0.542 which is lesser than the typical standard deviation for Likert scale of 5 points. This means that the ratings obtained in this study are close from mean, indicating smaller variations of the respondents'

responses (Wittink & Bayer, 1994).

Level of Motivational Strategies

Presented in Table 2 are the mean scores of motivational strategies. Data show that the overall mean is 3.94 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This implies that the level of motivational strategies of school heads in Talaingod District is high described as much observed.

Among the indicators, Staff development is classified as having the highest mean score of 4.08 defined as high. It is preceded with Staff recognition with a mean of 3.91 and Professional advancement with a mean of 3.83, all described as high.

Table 2. *Level of Motivational Strategies*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Staff Development	4.08	0.653	High
Staff Recognition	3.91	0.859	High
Professional Advancement	3.83	0.776	High
Overall	3.94	0.702	High

As presented in Table 2, it shows that the item giving a chance to enhance my skills and knowledge got the highest mean score of 4.19 which described as high.

The second highest item is giving a chance to attend in-service training courses from time to time has a mean score of 4.16 described as high. The third highest item is providing with opportunities for professional growth like studies got the mean score of 4.12 described as high. It is followed by the item providing with sufficient resources and support available to take important professional development activities has a mean score of 3.98 described as high. The item with the lowest mean score is providing with all trainings necessary for me to perform my job got a mean score of 3.93 described as high.

Reflected as well are the items of the second indicator with its respective mean score. The item able to take pride in a job well done acquired the highest mean score of 3.98 described as high. The second highest items able to get credit and praise for doing work well and valued and appreciated at my workplace got the mean score of 3.92 described as high. It is followed by the item adequately recognized for my good work with a mean score 3.88 described as high. The lowest mean score is reflected on the item recognized properly that has a mean score of 3.87 described as high.

As conferred are the last items of the last indicator. The highest mean score of 4.13 is manifested on the item given chance to participate in conferences, seminars, workshops and other related activities described as high. The second highest item is given chance to continue to learn has a mean score of 4.02 described as high. The third highest item It is given various opportunities for advancement has a mean score 3.89 described as high. It is followed by the item given opportunity for advancement based on standards with a mean score 3.78 described as high. The lowest mean score of 3.33 is on the item granted study leave for professional growth described as moderate.

The mean score ranges from 4.20-5.0 implies that the school head’s motivational strategies are very much observed. If the mean score ranges 3.40-4.19, it shows that the school head’s motivational strategies are much observed. Also, if it ranges from 2.60-3.39, it manifests that the school head’s motivational strategies are moderately observed. Moreover, if it ranges from 1.80-2.59, it reveals that the school head’s motivational strategies are less observed. Lastly, if the mean score ranges from 1.00-1.79, it connotes that the school head’s motivational strategies are not observed.

Level of Job Satisfaction

Table 3 presents the level of job satisfaction of public elementary school teachers in Talaingod District .Data show that the overall mean is 4.08 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that, in Talaingod District, the level of job satisfaction of public elementary teachers is high or much satisfied.

Data further show that among the indicators, Co-worker relations earned the highest weighted mean of 4.40 described as very high. It is preceded by Work itself with a mean of 4.07, Supervisor support with a mean of 3.96 and Advancement opportunities with a mean of 3.91 which are described as high.

Table 3. *Level of Job Satisfaction*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Work Itself	4.07	0.812	High
Advancement Opportunities	3.91	0.864	High
Supervisor Support	3.96	0.945	High
Co-Worker Relations	4.40	0.694	Very High
Overall	4.08	0.833	High

As presented in the Table 3, it shows that the item provided chance to work independently got the highest mean score of 4.27 described as high. The second highest item is informed with the policies and practices of the school has a mean of 4.07 described as high. The third highest item is provided with opportunity to use variety of skills got the mean score of 4.01 described as high. The lowest mean

score of 3.99 is on the items given freedom to make judgment and decision and able to utilized school facilities (classrooms, library, laboratories and others) described as high.

Reflected as well are the items of the second indicator with its respective mean score. The items provided with fair opportunity for promotion and given ample chances to meet standards for promotion acquired the highest mean score of 3.95 described as high. The second highest mean score is the item granted with opportunities for professional growth through formal education with a mean score of 3.94 described as high. It is followed by the item given chance to be reclassified or be promoted with a mean score of 3.93 described as high. The lowest mean score of 3.76 is reflected on the item informed clearly about the promotion system described as high.

It is also shown in the items covered by the third indicator. The highest mean score of 4.07 is manifested on the item imparted with suggestions to improve teaching described as high. The second highest mean score of 3.98 and described as high is on the item given feedback on my performances. The third highest item is given immediate assistance when needed help got the mean score of 3.96 described as high. It is followed by the item provided with equal treatment with a mean score of 3.91 described as high. The lowest mean score of 3.86 is on the item given materials needed for instruction regularly described as high.

As conferred are the items of the last indicator. Indicated on the table that the highest mean score of 4.43 described as high is reflected on the item able to get along with colleagues. The second highest item is encouraged to keep going and do better work has a mean score of 4.42 described as high. The third highest item is having good relationship with my co-workers got the mean score of 4.41 described as high. It is followed by the item provided with suggestions or feedbacks to improve my performance has a mean score of 4.40 described as high. The item with the lowest mean score is treated as one in the group got a mean score of 4.36 described as high.

The mean score ranges from 4.20-5.0 implies that the level of satisfaction of teachers towards their work is very much satisfied. If the mean score ranges 3.40-4.19, it shows that the level of satisfaction of teachers towards their work is much satisfied. Also, if it ranges from 2.60-3.39, it manifests that the level of satisfaction of teachers towards their work is moderately satisfied. Moreover, if it ranges from 1.80-2.59, it reveals that the level of satisfaction of teachers towards their work is less satisfied. Lastly, if the mean score ranges from 1.00-1.79, it connotes that the level of satisfaction of teachers towards their work is not satisfied.

Significance on the Relationship between Motivational Strategies and Job Satisfaction

Presented in Table 4 is the computation using the Pearson-r. Staff recognition gets the highest r-value of 0.856. It is followed by Professional advancement with an r-value of 0.809 and Staff development with r-value of 0.759. Furthermore, the level of likelihood of workforce growth, recognition of workers and professional progression is equal to 0.000 which is below the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between motivational strategies of school heads and job satisfaction of public elementary teachers in the Talaingod District is rejected. Further, this means that there is a significant relationship between motivational strategies of school heads and job satisfaction of public elementary teachers in Talaingod District.

Table 4. Significance on the Relationship between Motivational Strategies and Job Satisfaction

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	r-value	r squared	P-value	Decision
Staff Development	Job Satisfaction	0.759*	0.576	0.000	Ho is rejected
Staff Recognition		0.856*	0.733	0.000	Ho is rejected
Professional Advancement		0.809*	0.654	0.000	Ho is rejected

*p<0.05

Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Motivational Strategies to Job Satisfaction

Multiple regressions has been utilized to verify which of the motivational approaches metrics better influences work satisfaction of elementary school teachers in Talaingod District. Table 5 summarizes the results. The regression analysis with three indicators namely: Staff development, Staff recognition and Professional advancement yielded an adjusted r-square of 0.796 and 209.291 F-value with a probability value of 0.000 which is lesser than the significance level of 0.05. As the P-value is below 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected, which states that there is no domain in school heads' motivational strategies that significantly affects the job satisfaction of public elementary teachers in Talaingod District.

Table 5. Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Domains of Motivational Strategies to Job Satisfaction

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	P-value	Decision
	B	SE				
(continuous)						
Staff Development	0.115	0.055	0.127*	2.104	0.037	Ho is rejected
Staff Recognition	0.359	0.042	0.52*	8.605	0.000	Ho is rejected
Professional Advancement	0.239	0.047	0.314*	5.078	0.000	Ho is rejected

Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

R=0.892

F-ratio= 209.291

R2= 0.796

P-value= 0.000

Staff recognition achieved the maximum standardized beta coefficient of 0.52 with a probability value of 0.000 which is lesser than

the significance point of 0.05. It is preceded by Professional advancement obtaining a standardized beta coefficient of 0.314 and a probability value of 0.000 which is below the significance level of 0.05. This means that all domains of motivational strategies are all predictors of job satisfaction. Moreover, the study shows that all domains of motivational strategies of school heads influence job satisfaction of public elementary teachers and Staff recognition has the most influence to job satisfaction of public elementary teachers in Talaingod District.

Conclusions

In reference to the results of the research, it outlines the following assertions: the level of motivational strategies of school heads in Talaingod District is high. Also, public elementary teachers in Talaingod District have a high degree of job satisfaction.

Hence, motivational strategies and job satisfaction are closely related. Likewise, among the domains of motivational strategies: staff development, staff recognition and professional advancement, all domains significantly predicted job satisfaction and also has the most influence to job satisfaction of public elementary teachers in Talaingod District.

Grounded on the aforementioned outcomes of this study and derived inferences, the researcher recommends the following:

Among the three indicators of motivational strategies, professional advancement has the lowest mean mainly in item number 2- granted study leave for professional growth. It recommends that school heads will strengthen leave privileges for teachers particularly in line with studies and other academic means for professional growth. Moreover, they are encouraged to regularly conduct needs assessment to identify areas most needed, provide more conferences, seminars, workshops and other enhancement activities and offer educational courses and programs.

On the other hand, among the four indicators of job satisfaction, advancement opportunities gets the lowest mean mainly in item number 3- informed clearly about the promotion system. It recommends that school heads may present and discuss guidelines on promotions to the teachers through Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions and other means of information dissemination.

In as much as there is an significant relationship between motivational strategies and job satisfaction, it is essential to note that aligning work with appropriate approaches helps determine motivational strategies in job satisfaction of teachers. But equally important are the decisions that the school heads make about how to use best motivational strategies for what purposes and how they define their roles as administrator, same with the teachers about how best to adopt the strategies and how they deal with the work. And so, though the result is high, there is a possibility that job satisfaction of teachers will backslide if the administrators will neglect to monitor the factors. For this reason, the researcher recommends to continually develop and study the benefits of motivational strategies and better assess the satisfaction level of teachers to sustain and even increase effectiveness, productivity and commitment towards work.

Since all the domains of motivational strategies significantly predict the job satisfaction of teachers, the school heads may increase the high level of motivational strategies to a very high level and sustain similar through making plans and designs as to how to properly implement particular strategies.

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